

Effect of Ownership Diversity on Financial Stability of Listed Consumer Goods Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

Shareholders are always regarded as corporate owners, while directors are agents or representatives of shareholders who are supposed to allocate business resources in a way to increase their wealth. In Nigeria, several issues related to the governance and management of companies have been identified. These problems range from errors and mistakes to outright fraud. The origins of these problems range from concentrated ownership, weak incentives, and poor protection of minority shareholders to weak information standards. This study examines the effect of ownership structure diversity on financial stability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The study adopts an ex-post facto research design using panel data from ten years, 2014-2023, to examine the effect of independent variables, institutional ownership, ownership concentration and foreign ownership, on the dependent variable, financial stability. The population of the study consist of all consumer goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Limited as of 31st December 2023. In view of this, sixteenth (16) consumer goods firms listed on Nigerian Exchange Limited were selected to represent the sample size for this study using a purposive sampling technique based on the criterion that consumer goods firms must be listed and disclose all the data needed for the study in the annual reports. Secondary data was used, and data was sourced from the audited annual reports and accounts of the sample consumer goods firms. The multiple regression technique was used with the aid of EViews 10 to analyze the data. The findings show that institutional ownership has a negative and insignificant effect on the financial stability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Ownership concentration and foreign ownership have negative and significant effects on the financial stability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The study recommends that there is a need to extensively increase institutional shareholding, concentrated shareholding and foreign shareholding of the listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria as not only a way to increase the share of the firms but as a way of encouraging them to increase their efficiency.

Keywords: Institutional ownership, Ownership concentration, Foreign ownership.

Introduction

Financial stability is one of the most topical issues in today's financial literature owing to the need for firms to continue to fulfill both short term and long-term financial commitment on one hand and the need to salvage firms from the monstrous tendencies of distress and collapse on the other hand. Also, the ownership structure is a formidable driver of financial stability (Salehi, et al, 2017). Adegbe, et al (2019) posited that financial stability has relative or absolute size that cannot be neglected in profit making organizations. This study brings into reminiscence the previous scenarios of corporate scandals like Enron (2001) an energy company where directors and executives fraudulently concealed large losses in Enron's projects (Shaughnessy, 2011). Another was WorldCom (2001), a telecommunications firm in which after falling share prices and a failed share redemption scheme, it was discovered that the directors had used fraudulent accounting methods to push up the stock price (Verizon, 2004). Also is Parmalat (2003) of Italy.

Others according to Shaughnessy (2011) includes waste management scandal (1998), Tyco scandal (2002), Health south scandal (2003), Freddie Mac scandal (2003), American insurance group scandal (2005), Lehman brothers' scandal (2008), Bernie Madoff scandal (2008), Saytam scandal (2009). The collapse of most of the companies bothers on corporate governance and ethical breach (Shaughnessy, 2011). The Nigerian firms are not insulated from the quagmire of scandals where this study established cases like Cadbury Nigeria (2006), Unilever Nigeria (2002), Stanbic IBTC (2018), Skye Bank (2018) and Theranos (2018). The relevance of analysis on financial stability was underscored during the international financial crunch at the end of the 1990s (Nemzeti, 2018). These developments prompted the need for continuous provision to the professional public opinion with an up-to-date and reliable picture of the condition of a given country's financial sector (Nemzeti, 2018; Oyedokun, Tade, Eso, & Abiodun-Afolabi, 2024).

The inability of the firm in meeting with the overheads and other running costs poses a threat to the solvency and going concern concept of the concern. Even where managers are involved in the

ownership status of the business, it is the quality of their involvement in credibility and stewardship that might help to sustain the business from the shackles and stronghold of bankruptcy. The nexus of ownership structure and performance has received considerable attention by researchers all over the world (Chung, Firth & Kim 2002; Kumar, 2003; Hu & Izumida, 2008; Oyedokun, Idowu, Abiodun-Afolabi, & Eso, 2024). Ownership structure has received much attention because it is part of the agency theory and corporate governance. Jiang (2004) investigated the effect of ownership structure on the performance of listed companies in Heilongjiang Province. The results of the study showed that the different forms of ownership may have implications for corporate governance and financial stability of firms.

Firms are established and continuously governed and monitored to enable them to achieve their objectives (Hu & Izumida, 2008; & Al-Najjar, 2015). Fama and Jensen (1983) stated that organizations compete for survival, and the form of organization that survives in an activity is the one that delivers the product demanded by customers at an acceptable price while covering costs. The concept of financial stability is perceived to depend so much on the ownership structure upon which the future affairs of the business rest. There is a simplistic believe that where business, institution, family or foreign owners of firms are directly or indirectly involved in the affair of piloting or paddling the activities of the day to day running of their businesses, there is an appreciable tendency that they would ensure a significant proportion of the financial stability of the firm that is tailored towards the attainment of the goals and objectives of the business. Many studies have delved more on institutional ownership, concentration and foreign ownership which by category could be termed primary ownership. The motivation of this research is to look at the effect of the ownership diversity on financial stability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Financial Stability

According to Mosser, et al (2018), financial stability refers to the ability of the financial system “to facilitate and enhance economic processes, manage risks, and absorb shocks. Central Bank of Nigeria (2018) defines financial stability as the resiliency of the financial system to unanticipated adverse shocks while enabling the continuing smooth functioning of the financial system intermediation process. It further stressed that a stable financial system contributes to broader economic growth and rising living standards and that the financial system performs one of the most important functions in the welfare of its citizens by supporting the ability of households and firms to hold and transfer financial assets with confidence.

Conceptually, financial stability entails the ability to pay overhead expenses, settle debts as and when due and pay returns on capital to investors (Salawu, 2017). Salawu (2017) further stressed that though it goes beyond the financial aspect (e.g. retaining relevant employees and customer assenting the production process for cost saving etc. Thus, it is the review of cash flows statement which some financial ratios can do. Financial stability according to Salawu (2017), includes paying overhead cost, settling debt, return on capital and retain for growth. There is just a thin line between financial stability and financial risk. A concern with a high financial risk will most likely experience low financial stability while firms with a low financial risk will most likely have high financial stability. The solvency state of a firm has a lot to do with the financial risk cum financial stability of the firm. A firm that is solvent is perceived to be more responsible in settling debt obligation as they fall due as such could be adjudged to have high financial stability compared to another firm that is distant away from solvency. The solvency position of a firm has a lot to do with its liquidity which is so much tied to the methods and durations of collections from the debtor’s average collection period.

However, Muriungi, et al, (2017) defined financial stability as a condition in which the mechanisms of the economy for pricing, allocating, and managing financial, credit, liquidity, counterpart and market risks are functioning well enough to contribute to the performance of the economy (Oyedokun, & Amoo, 2023). They highlighted three major areas involved in comprehensive assessment of financial stability to include identification of the plausible and systemically important sources of risks and vulnerabilities that could pose challenges to financial stability in future; an appraisal of the potential costs in case some combination of these identified risks and vulnerabilities materialize and forming a judgment about the individual and collective strengths and robustness of the constituent parts of the financial system, institutions, markets and infrastructures.

Ownership Diversity

Ownership diversity is defined by Jensen and Meckling (1976) as the distribution of equity with respect to capital, voting rights, and the identities of equity owners. The aforementioned was mentioned in their study on the relationship between equity and the type of agency costs in order to incorporate concepts into the preliminary stages of a theory on corporate ownership diversity. Because of the increased dynamics of corporate ownership portfolios, interest in ownership diversity has increased recently. A corporation's ownership diversity is regarded as a corporate governance tool that can improve a company's productivity and has been shown to improve the performance of the company in question. Jensen and Meckling (1976) argued that joint-stock companies are less efficient than private co-partner companies because their directors might not manage other people's money with the same level of caution that they do their own. The principal-agent theory deals with the possible conflict that could exist between management and shareholders (Idowu, Abiodun-Afolabi, Eso, & Oyedokun, 2024).

The fundamental cause of the conflict can be traced back to the differing goals of managers and shareholders, specifically in relation to how control rights and cash flow rights are divided.

Different definitions of ownership diversity have been proposed by academics. Ownership diversity is defined by Oyejide and Soyibo (2001) as the configuration of equity owners, emphasizing both private and state-owned ownership. They have distinguished between two categories of ownership diversities: privately held and state-owned. Ownership diversity, according to Mitra (2002), is the composition of people or organizations that own equity shares. The authors classify ownership diversity into institutional ownership, managerial structure, and block ownership in their examination of the relationship between ownership diversity and audit fees in the US market in 2000. The notion of ownership diversity, as stated by Joel et al. (2020), concerns the level of share concentration among managers, foreign entities, and government officials.

Institutional Ownership

One significant factor influencing a company's performance is institutional ownership. According to the literature, in order for institutional investors to fulfill their fiduciary duty, the projects in question must enhance the company's governance and management's transparency while focusing on maximizing shareholder value. It goes without saying that institutional investors pick a solid project to fund in the hopes of increasing profits and returns. Additionally, they are crucial to corporate governance since they enforce stricter oversight of managers' performance or take charge of the business. Large investors that own a greater portion of the company are therefore more eager to keep an eye on management by having a voice on the board. According to the agency theory, institutional investor monitoring may be an important governance tool. Because institutional ownership is intelligent and offers advantages in information processing and acquisition, it effectively monitors management discretion and improves information competency in capital markets; Koh, 2003). This, in turn, lowers agency costs and restrains opportunism (Al-Najjar, 2010; Chung, et al, 2002; Shleifer & Vishny, 1997). Additionally, by providing other shareholders with greater information about the company, institutional investors significantly lower the cost of

external monitoring. Moreover, they have much influence on the decisions concerning their large investment in companies.

Ownership Concentration

Ownership concentration is the percentage of a company's ownership that is held by shareholders who either have a majority stake or a controlling interest. Concentration of ownership provides the ability and motivation for shareholders to oversee and influence management decisions. Therefore, by exercising greater caution in monitoring and safeguarding their investments, concentrated shareholders have the opportunity to reduce conflicts between managers and the company (Adebisi & Olowookere, 2016). The natural logarithm of the equity held by block holders' investors in the business represents ownership concentration.

Foreign Ownership

The term foreign ownership comprises all form of foreign private investment which confers control and ownership over a package of resources in a foreign country (Herbert, 1995). It has been suggested by (Liang & Weir, 1999; Estrin, et al, 2001) that foreign enterprises have superior ownership and internalization advantages (more business experience, technology, and capital, as well as management and entrepreneurial abilities) than their domestic equivalents. Foreign ownership, according to Chai (2010), is the proportion of shares held by foreign investors. Foreign ownership was defined by Tsegba and Achua (2011) as the inclusion of non-natives in a company's ownership diversity.

Foreign ownership refers to the situation where individuals, organizations, or entities from one country own assets, properties, businesses, or investments in another country (Herbert, 1995). These assets can include real estate, companies, stocks, bonds, natural resources, and intellectual property, among others. Foreign ownership can have both positive and negative implications for the host country and the foreign investors: (i) Capital infusion: Foreign investors can bring in

much-needed capital to the host country, promoting economic growth and development (Herbert, 1995). (ii) Job creation: Foreign-owned businesses may generate employment opportunities for local citizens, reducing unemployment rates (Herbert, 1995). (iii) Technology transfer: Foreign companies often bring advanced technologies and know-how, which can help improve the host country's technological capabilities (Herbert, 1995). (iv) Market access: Foreign-owned companies can provide easier access to international markets, potentially boosting exports from the host country (Herbert, 1995). (v) Diversification: Foreign ownership can diversify the host country's economic landscape, reducing its dependence on specific industries or sectors (Herbert, 1995).

Institutional Ownership and Financial Stability

Abdul, et al (2021) looked at the ownership diversity and financial stability of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Reliability of the ownership diversity variables on the company's financial stability was measured using Return on Asset as a proxy. The study employed a sample of thirty-five listed manufacturing firms. Nine years of annual reports and accounts of a chosen sample of manufacturing companies provided the data that was gathered and examined. Financial stability is positively and significantly impacted by institutional ownership, according to the study. The research advises institutional owners to keep using their power and knowledge to rein in management misconduct, which could have a detrimental effect on the operations of manufacturing companies listed in Nigeria. The study was only limited to manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Therefore, it is imperative to conduct similar studies using consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

According to Ud Din et al. (2021), who looked at how the ownership diversity affected the financial stability of 146 manufacturers listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange, institutional ownership and financial stability as measured by ROA and MBR significantly positively correlated, suggesting that institutional investors are crucial to performance improvement. They

gave credence to 146 manufacturers listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange. Therefore, there is need to conduct similar studies using consumer goods firm in Nigeria.

Ownership Concentration and Financial Stability

Shahwan et al. (2023) looked at how the ownership structure affected the 13 banks that were listed on the Egyptian Stock Exchange between 2016 and 2019. The characteristics of the ownership diversity were identified as concentration of ownership, administrative ownership, foreign ownership, government ownership, and institutional ownership. The researcher used the most recent standards to measure financial stability. Market Value Added (MVA), Added Economic Value (added), Tobin's Q, the investigation has produced a set of findings that can be summed up as follows: the prior period's financial stability impact agreement, as well as the ownership concentration, administrative ownership, foreign ownership, and government ownership for the three financial stability variables. Based on the differences in these variables effects between the economic value added and the market value added which are caused by the actual reverse correlation between the two the study discovered different effects of institutional ownership and the ratio of indebtedness among the three financial stability variables. The study was limited to 13 banks listed on the Egyptian Stock Exchange from 2016 to 2019 and the period of the study was short to generalise their findings.

Onuora, et al (2022) investigated the relationship which exists between ownership structure and financial stability of quoted non-financial firms in Nigeria. The study used an ex-post facto research design, and the data came from the 2012–2021 published annual financial reports of all consumer goods companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX). The ownership diversity was measured using institutional ownership, concentrated ownership, foreign ownership, and block ownership in order to ascertain the relationship between ownership diversity and financial stability. Return on equity (ROE) was used to represent the performance of the firms. According to the study's findings, which were derived using an OLS regression model, institutional

ownership, concentrated ownership, foreign ownership, and block ownership all significantly and negatively affect a financial stability as determined by return on equity (ROE) at the 1-5% significant level. The study comes to the conclusion that ownership diversity guarantees the financial success of businesses. This is regarded as solid and completed within the parameters of the current study with regard to the economy and sector. However, the current study is different in that it only looks at a subsector of the consumer goods industry rather than the entire industry over the period it covered. Not only is the current study timely, but it also encompasses the whole consumer goods industry.

Foreign Ownership and Financial Stability

Khaled, et al (2021) examined the relationship between ownership diversity and firm performance about manufacturing companies listed in Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE). Dynamic panel data from 15 chemical and pharmaceutical companies listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE) is used empirically in the analysis. The years of study were 2011–2020. Panel data regression analysis was used in the study. The study demonstrates that institutional ownership, concentration, and foreign ownership have a significant impact on the financial stability of the sampled companies as measured by ROA and ROE. In contrast, managerial ownership and insider ownership have a negative impact. The study found no evidence of a significant correlation between the performance of firms and the ownership of block holders. This study continues to play a vital role in comprehending the impact of ownership diversities on the performance of firms. More specifically the policymakers may consider the study for implementing the relevant issues. The study's results were restricted to 15 Bangladeshi pharmaceutical and chemical companies enlisted in DSE and could not be applied to other companies doing business in Bangladesh.

Suleiman and Nasamu (2021) looked at the impact of ownership diversity on the financial stability of listed Nigerian oil and gas companies from 2006 to 2019. The sample companies' financial reports and accounts were used to derive secondary data. To analyze the data, Robust ordinary

least square was employed as the best estimator of the regression model. The results showed that foreign ownership significantly improves the financial stability of Nigerian oil and gas companies. The study suggested that foreigners should be allowed to take the majority of the ownership diversity of listed oil and gas companies in the downstream sector of the petroleum industry in Nigeria, more so, management of these companies should formulate policies that would boost the number of shares allocated to foreigners since foreign ownership increases financial stability. The study was only limited to Nigerian oil and gas companies and their findings can only be valid for listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Therefore, it is imperative to conduct similar studies in other sectors, especially the consumer goods sector.

Pecking Order Theory (POT)

Pecking order theory was developed by Myers (1994). It states that organizations prioritize their sources of financing according to the law of least effort or of least resistance preferring to raise equity as a financing means 'of last resort'. To this end internal funds are used first and when that is fully utilized, debt is issued and when it is not sensible to issue any more debt, equity is issued. This theory maintains that businesses adhere to a hierarchy of financing sources and prefer internal financing when available and debt is preferred over equity if external financing is required. This theory has been supported by many authors like Asquith and Mullins (1986) and Eckbo (1986) where they showed evidence of adverse selection relating to equity issues. The work by Cadsby, et al, (1990) posited on similar evidence on experimental bases regarding the financial requirement of firms.

Also, Jibrán, et al, (2012) test the POT for the capital structure of listed firms. They established that POT in its strong form sustains that equity issues would never occur, whereas in its weak form limited amounts of issues are tolerable. The relevance of pecking order theory to this work is that the proportion of debt to equity cum the ownership structure that organizations should adopt will not pose a threat to the going concern concept of such concern but rather it would enable firms to

prioritize whether more of borrowings to equity should be employed to run the business or to have more equity holders than debt to run the business. The business may also decide on equal proportion of debt and equity that will be to the betterment of all stakeholders. The implication is that the Perking Order Theory (POT) will also be a litmus test into how managerial, institutional, family or foreign ownership will drive the financial stability of a firm. By so doing the order of ownership structure in terms of viability and potency will be known and as such management could be judiciously guided on how the ordering can be improvised.

Methodology

The study was designed to capture the effect of the ownership diversity on financial stability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. This study adopts ex-post facto research design because the design allows for the analysis of possible cause and effect among variables. The research design involves assessment of the relationships between theoretically related variables and observe the impact of the independent variable(s) on the dependent variable. The population of the study includes all the twenty-three (23) listed consumer goods firms operating on the Nigeria Exchange limited (NGX) from 2014 to 2023. Purposive sampling technique was used to arrive at the sample size of sixteen consumer goods firms based on a criterion that a company must be listed and disclosed all the data needed for the study in the annual report and accounts, selected companies are contained in Appendix A. The study utilized secondary data from the annual reports and audited accounts of the sampled listed consumer goods firms as at 31st December 2023. The technique of data analysis in this study is panel multiple regression. This is because the objective of the study is to evaluate the effect of ownership diversity on financial stability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Diagnostic tests including Hausman specification test, correlation metric, multicollinearity, Variance inflation factor, heteroskedasticity test were conducted.

Model Specification

The model of this study is consistent with Altman's Z-Score Model Formula (2005). The Z-score model is based on five key financial ratios, and it is written as follows:

$$\text{Z-Score} = (1.2 \times X_1) + (1.4 \times X_2) + (3.3 \times X_3) + 0.6 \times X_4 + (1 \times X_5).$$

Where:

X_1 = Working Capital + Total Asset

X_2 = Retained Earnings + Total Assets

X_3 = Earnings before Interest and Tax + Total Assets

X_4 = Market Value of Equity / Total Liabilities

X_5 = Sales + Total asset

The Altman Z-Score is a quantitative balance-sheet method of determining a company's financial health. "Safe" companies, i.e. companies that have a low probability of bankruptcy; have an Altman Z-Score greater than 3.0. The Altman Z-Score is a measure of a company's health and likelihood of bankruptcy. Several key ratios are used in the formulation of an Altman Z-Score Value. The model captures the direct effect of institutional ownership, ownership concentration and foreign ownership on financial stability. This model shall be used to test hypotheses. Expressing the specified linear equation, it is as follows:

$$FS_{it} = \beta_{0it} + \beta_1 IO_{it} + \beta_2 OWC_{it} + \beta_3 FO_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

β_1 - β_3 = are the parameters estimate or coefficients in equation,

IO = Institutional Ownership

OWC = Ownership Concentration

FO = Foreign Ownership

μ_{it} = error term.

Variables Measurement

Variables	Measurement	Source
Financial Stability	The Altman Z-score, a variation of the traditional z-score in statistics, is based on five financial ratios that can be calculated from data found on a company's annual report. The formula for Altman Z-Score is $1.2 * (\text{working capital} / \text{total assets}) + 1.4 * (\text{retained earnings} / \text{total assets}) + 3.3 * (\text{earnings before interest and tax} / \text{total assets}) + 0.6 * (\text{market value of equity} / \text{total liabilities}) + 1.0 * (\text{sales} / \text{total assets})$.	Altman, (2005)
Institutional Ownership (IO)	Number of shares owned by the institution divided by Number of outstanding shares multiply by x 100%	Musa (2014)
Ownership Concentration (OWC)	Represented by natural log of shares owned by individuals with block vote.	Baba (2016)
Foreign Ownership (FO)	Measured as the total of shares held by foreigner divided by the total number of shareholdings.	Salehi, et al (2012)

Source: Author’s Compilation 2025

Results and Discussions

Descriptive Statistics

	FS	IO	OWC	FO
Mean	4.269956	0.270112	0.654499	0.356665
Median	4.249400	0.235200	0.355750	0.206800
Maximum	11.45920	0.565210	4.910400	6.448500
Minimum	0.058600	0.091170	0.000500	0.000500
Std. Dev.	3.212913	0.133432	0.849409	0.645289
Skewness	0.348751	0.533380	2.542340	6.283572
Kurtosis	1.964807	2.094820	9.562215	53.54443

Jarque-Bera	10.38756	13.04884	459.4442	17971.46
Probability	0.005551	0.001467	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	683.1929	43.21786	104.7199	56.70976
Sum Sq. Dev.	1641.327	2.830835	114.7179	65.79081
Observations	160	160	160	160

Source: EViews 10 Output 2025

Table 1 confirms the descriptive statistics of different variables studied with an emphasis on Mean, Maximum, Minimum, standard deviation and the test of Jarque-Bera result. The result revealed that the mean values financial stability proxy by Z- Scores (FS), institutional ownership (IO), ownership concentration (OWC) and foreign ownership (FO) stood at 4.269956, 0.270112, 0.654499 and 0.356665 respectively. The Jarque-Bera probabilities in the respective cases indicate that the data are normal. This is evident in the probabilities of less than 0.05.

Correlation Analysis

	FS	IO	OWC	FO
FS	1.000000			
IO	-0.053788	1.000000		
OWC	-0.454508	-0.128487	1.000000	
FO	-0.198020	-0.092605	0.029004	1.000000

Source: EViews 10 Output 2025

The correlation result indicates that institutional ownership (IO), ownership concentration (OWC) and foreign ownership are negatively correlated to financial stability (FS). This implies that the variables (institutional ownership, ownership concentration and foreign ownership move in the inverse direction with financial stability.

Post Residual Diagnostics Test

Multicollinearity

Variance Inflation Factors

Date: 02/17/25 Time: 18:48

Sample: 1 160

Included observations: 160

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Uncentered VIF	Centered VIF
C	0.333229	6.811029	NA
IO	2.812442	5.211180	1.017065
OWC	0.069476	1.626470	1.018161
FO	0.275825	1.576854	1.002911

Source: EViews 10 Output 2025

The VIF for IO, OWC and FO are 1.01, 1.01 and 1.00 respectively. This indicates that, the VIF are less than 10 respectively. Thus, the study concludes that there is no problem of multicollinearity. That multicollinearity exists only when the VIF is greater than 10

Heteroskedasticity Test

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	0.648253	Prob. F (3,156)	0.5852
Obs*R-squared	1.970066	Prob. Chi-Square (3)	0.5786
Scaled explained SS	1.257975	Prob. Chi-Square (3)	0.7391

Source: EViews 10 Output 2025

The Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test reveals heteroskedasticity, as seen in the table. The F-statistic value is 0.648 with a probability value of 0.58. The observed R-squared value is 1.970 with a probability chi-square value of 0.57. The value of Scaled explained SS is 1.257 with a corresponding probability chi-square value of 0.73 infers that there is no problem of Heteroskedasticity in the residual.

Hausman Specification Test

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test

Equation: Untitled

Test cross-section random effects

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	17.721909	3	0.0005

Cross-section random effects test comparisons:

Variable	Fixed	Random	Var (Diff.)	Prob.
IO	-1.938414	-1.926880	0.039201	0.9535
OWC	0.333671	0.130376	0.003171	0.0003
FO	-0.024843	-0.066940	0.000241	0.0067

Source: EViews 10 Output 2025

The Hausman specification test was used to determine whether the fixed effects model (FE) or the random effects model (RE) was the best fit. Given the Chi-Sq (3) value of 17.72190 and the accompanying probability Chi-Sq value of 0.0005, which is less than 0.05 percent significant threshold, the Hausman Test suggests that the fixed effect model is more appropriate than the random effect model.

Table 3 Regression Result

Dependent Variable: FS

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 02/17/25 Time: 17:59

Sample: 2014 2023

Periods included: 10

Cross-sections included: 16

Total panel (unbalanced) observations: 160

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	6.600849	0.574190	11.49593	0.0000

IO	-3.161547	1.680009	-1.881863	0.0617
OWC	-1.753971	0.262828	-6.673468	0.0000
FO	-0.977587	0.345425	-2.830095	0.0053
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R-squared	0.257731	Mean dependent var	4.244391	
Adjusted R-squared	0.243364	S.D. dependent var	3.206698	
S.E. of regression	2.789340	Akaike info criterion	4.914323	
Sum squared resid	1205.965	Schwarz criterion	4.991528	
Log likelihood	-386.6887	Hannan-Quinn criter.	4.945675	
F-statistic	17.93969	Durbin-Watson stat	0.528479	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: EViews 10 Output 2025

The overall fitness of the model as shown in the F-statistic of 17.93969 with Prob (F-statistic) of 0.000000 is statistically significant as it is less than the standard critical p-value of 0.05 therefore, the functional specification of the model is appropriate. The R-squared, which shows the overall explanatory power of the model, reveals that the independent variables (institutional ownership, ownership concentration and foreign ownership,) explain about 25% of the systematic variation of the dependent variable, while 75% is attributed to stochastic error variances or the error margin.

From the computed regression result shows that institutional ownership (IO) has negative and insignificant effect on financial stability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria, from the coefficient of -3.161547 and t-statistics of -1.881863 and the probability value of 0.0617 which is greater than 0.05 percent (the level of significant). It means a unit change in institutional ownership will cause a decrease in financial stability. Similarly, the regression result also indicates that ownership concentration (OWC) has negative and significant effect on financial stability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria, from the coefficient of -1.753971 and t-statistics of -6.673468 and the probability value of 0.0000 which is less than 0.05 percent (the level of significant). It means a unit change in ownership concentration will cause a decrease in financial stability of listed consumer goods firm. Furthermore, Foreign ownership (FO), has negative and significant effect

on financial stability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria, from the coefficient of -0.977587 and t-statistics of -2.830095 and probability of 0.0053 which is less than 0.05 percent (the level of significant). It means a unit change in managerial ownership will cause an increase in financial stability.

Discussion of the Findings

The results of this study indicate a negative and significant effect between institutional ownership and financial stability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. By implication, Institutional ownership has no effect on financial stability. It is shown from the analysis, because institutional ownership has no effect in increasing financial stability, companies with high institutional ownership value do not necessarily have high financial stability. Institutional ownership only shows how many shares in a company are owned by institutions. The effectiveness of share ownership of a company by institutional investors cannot be ascertained in monitoring the behavior of managers because investor access is limited, while more detailed and accurate company information is obtained by company managers (managers) as shown in this study. The conclusion of this study is that institutional ownership has no effect on financial stability.

Similarly, the study findings show that ownership concentration has a negative and significant effect on financial stability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The findings indicate that ownership concentration has no effect on financial stability because a low level of ownership concentration indicates a negative signal given by the company to stakeholders, this can later affect investment decisions. In accordance with signaling theory which explains that companies provide signals to users of financial statements, especially to investors who will make investments. Empirical results show that ownership concentration partially has no effect on financial stability Onuora, et al (2022)

Furthermore, foreign ownership of the sampled listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria is negatively impacted by financial stability. The findings agree with the trade-off theory which explains that if the ownership position is below the optimal point, then any additional debt will increase financial stability. Conversely, if the ownership diversity position is above the optimal point, then any additional debt will decrease financial stability. Therefore, assuming the optimal structure target has not been achieved, based on the trade-off theory, it predicts a positive relationship to financial stability. This research is in line with research conducted by Suleiman and Nasamu (2021) which shows that foreign ownership has a negative and significant effect on financial stability.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study concludes that institutional ownership, ownership concentration and foreign ownership influence the company's financial stability. Analyzing the relationship between the variables, it is observed that there is a negative relationship between institutional ownership, ownership concentration, foreign ownership and financial stability of listed consumer goods in Nigeria. The study recommends that the increase in the stability of company will be greater if the debt from the company can also increase profitability from the company, provided that the debt does not exceed its optimal point.

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APPENDIX ‘A’
Population of the Study

N/S	Population for the Study
1	Champion Brewery Plc
2	Golden Guinea Brewery Plc
3	Guinness Nigeria Plc
4	International Brewery Plc
5	DN Tyre & Rubber Plc
6	Nigerian Breweries Plc
7	Nigerian Enamelware Plc
8	7 Up Bottling Company Plc
9	Vita Foam Nigeria Plc
10	Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc
11	Flour Mills Nigeria Plc
12	Honeywell Flour Mill Plc
13	P. Z. Cussons Nigeria Plc
14	Multi – Trex Integrated Foods Plc
15	Nascon Allied Industries Plc
16	Northern Nigeria Flour Mills Plc
17	Dangote Flour Mills Plc
18	Union Dicon Salt Plc
19	U.T.C. Nigeria Plc
20	Menichols Plc
21	Unilever Nigeria Plc
22	Cadbury Nigeria Plc
23	Nestle Nigeria Plc